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Advancing Capacity & Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies Post-2027

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POLICY BRIEF

Key messages

- Evidence-based policymaking under the EU's Better Regulation agenda demands being supported by advanced, holistic models that account for economic, environmental, and social factors.
- Policy innovation is needed to address climate, biodiversity, health, and equity concerns, requiring robust data, stakeholder alignment, and scenario analysis.
- Current policy-relevant scientific challenges include modelling the integrated environmental, social and economic impacts of CAP changes, allowing an improved understanding of potential trade-offs between policy objectives.
- ACT4CAP27 aims to enhance capacity and tools for analyzing the impacts of CAP reforms, focusing on sustainability, stakeholder engagement, and future-proofing EU agri-food policies.

What is the issue?

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is central to shaping Europe's agricultural sector, yet traditional policy analysis tools often fail to address its multifaceted impacts on sustainability, equity, and resilience.

As Europe gears up for the post-2027 CAP reform, challenges like climate change, biodiversity loss, income inequality, and rural demographics demand a systemic and forward-looking approach.

Current models often lack the granularity to reflect regional variations and the transformative impacts of emerging technologies, sustainability measures, and geopolitical shifts, including Ukraine's potential accession to the EU.

ACT4CAP27 is a European research project aiming to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community, to provide support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027. | Project timeframe: 01/03/2024 – 28/02/2029

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Why is this important?

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) faces a critical juncture as Europe navigates pressing sustainability challenges. Effective CAP policies are essential to mitigate climate impacts, curb greenhouse gas emissions, and reverse biodiversity loss, all of which are vital to achieving Europe's environmental commitments.

At the same time, these policies must prioritize equity and inclusion, as ecological transitions may disproportionately burden smaller farms and vulnerable rural communities, deepening income disparities.

Moreover, Europe's global competitiveness is at stake, with emerging challenges such as geopolitical tensions, trade disruptions, and shifting consumer preferences toward sustainable diets demanding strategic adaptability.

A lack of robust, real-time data and comprehensive scenario planning hampers the effectiveness of policy interventions, limiting the CAP's ability to respond swiftly and effectively to a rapidly changing agri-food landscape.

What can policy makers do?

- 1. Enhance Modelling and Data Integration.** Invest in tools that reflect regional, social, and economic nuances. Align CAP analysis with global frameworks like the IPCC's SSP scenarios for consistency and relevance. Incorporate real-time data on eco-scheme adoption, digital innovations, and agricultural education trends.
- 2. Address Environmental and Social Goals.** Develop clear benchmarks for biodiversity, soil health, and emissions reductions. Integrate nature-based solutions and agroforestry into CAP frameworks. Address demographic challenges by incentivizing technology adoption among younger and older farmers.
- 3. Support Strategic Dialogue and Stakeholder Engagement.** Use platforms like ACT4CAP27 to facilitate collaboration among policymakers, researchers, and farmers. Prioritize policies with broad stakeholder support, including innovative payments for ecosystem services and sustainable diets. Expand scenario analysis to include geopolitical factors, such as Ukraine's accession and its impact on EU trade, standards, and sustainability goals.
- 4. Reform Incentives and Payments.** Transition from area-based subsidies to results-driven payments aligned with environmental and climate targets. Introduce complementary measures, such as carbon taxes or eco-scheme rewards, to drive adoption of sustainable practices. Address trade-offs in policy coherence (e.g. reducing sugar subsidies while considering consumer taxation impacts).
- 5. Promote Knowledge Transfer and Innovation.** Enhance agricultural education and training, focusing on digitalization and sustainability. Foster knowledge-sharing networks between current EU states and potential new members like Ukraine. Support research on alternative farming practices, such as organic farming, green fertilizers, and digital solutions.

References and further reading

<https://act4cap27.eu>

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